

XII

CONGRESSO

CONGRESO

IBÉRICO DE GEOQUÍMICA

Extended Abstracts

22 - 26 Setembro de 2019
Septiembre

Évora, Portugal

CIG 2019

XII Congresso Ibérico de Geoquímica | XX Semana da Geoquímica

22-26 setembro de 2019, Évora, Portugal

Extended Abstracts

Editores

Pedro Nogueira, Noel Moreira, José Roseiro, Miguel Maia

Design

Miguel Maia, Diogo São Pedro

ISBN

978-972-778-121-8

1ª Edição

O depósito cuprífero do Barrigão: tenantite-tetraedrite para aplicações termoeléctricas e de alta tecnologia

The Barrigão copper deposit: tennantite-tetrahedrite for thermoelectric and high-technology applications

De Oliveira, D.¹, Salgueiro, R.¹, Silva, T.P.¹, Reiser, F.², Guimarães, F.³, Neves, F.⁴

¹ Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia, Unidade de Recursos Minerais e Geofísica, Estrada da Portela, Bairro do Zambujal – Alfragide, Apartado 7586, 2610-999 Amadora, Portugal

² ProGraphite GmbH, Dr.-Schindler-Str. 9, 94107 Untergriesbach, Germany

³ Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia, Unidade de Ciência e Tecnologia Mineral, Rua da Amieira, 4465-021 S. Mamede de Infesta, Portugal

⁴ Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia, Unidade de Energias Renováveis e Integração de Sistemas de Energia, Estrada do Paço do Lumiar, 22, 1649-038 Lisboa, Portugal

* daniel.oliveira@lneg.pt

Resumo: O depósito filoniano de cobre re-mobilizado do Barrigão é revisitado à luz da importância da tetraedrite-tenantite como fonte de matérias-primas críticas (MPC) da UE, bem como a pesquisa de materiais para o desenvolvimento de tecnologias colectoras de energia termoeléctrica (TE) e solar. A transição para economias descarbonizadas (+ e-mobilidade) e a completa implementação da economia circular implica inovação contínua em materiais e em tecnologias de energia com baixo teor de carbono. A continuada importância estratégica das matérias-primas para a indústria transformadora da UE, o antimónio, entre outras 25 matérias-primas minerais, foi adicionado à lista mais recente de MPC. O Barrigão está estruturalmente associado a uma zona de falha tardi varisca com orientação NE-SW. O minério, tipo brecha, com até quatro estágios de deposição, é dominado por calcopirite + tenantite-tetraedrite, com arsenopirite, pirite e löllingite. Amostras compostas seleccionadas da escombreira foram moídas (1-2 e 2-4 mm) e os grãos de tetraedrite-tenantite foram extraídos e caracterizados química e mineralogicamente para serem aplicados em testes para produzir materiais TE.

Palavras-chave: Barrigão, antimónio, tenantite-tetraedrite, materiais termoeléctricos, matérias-primas críticas

Abstract: The Barrigão re-mobilised copper vein deposit is revisited in the light of tetrahedrite-tennantite importance for EU Critical Raw Materials (CRM) knowledge as well as material research for development of thermoelectric (TE) and solar energy harvesting technologies. The transition to decarbonised economies (+ e-mobility) and full circular economy implementation implies continuous innovation in materials and in low-C energy technologies. The continued strategic importance of raw materials for the EU manufacturing industry, antimony, amongst another 25 mineral raw materials, was added to the latest list of CRM. Barrigão is structurally associated with an inferred late Variscan NE–SW striking fault zone. The ore, dominated by chalcopyrite + tennantite-tetrahedrite, with minor arsenopyrite, pyrite, and löllingite, is a breccia-type ore, characterised by up to four ore-forming stages. Hand selected composite mine dump samples were crushed (1-2 and 2-4 mm) from where tetrahedrite-tennantite grains were handpicked and chemically and mineralogically characterised for application in future tests to produce TE materials.

Keywords: Barrigão, antimony, tennantite-tetrahedrite, thermoelectric materials, CRM

1. Introduction

Raw materials are crucial to world economies. They form a strong industrial base, producing a broad range of goods and applications used in everyday life and modern technologies. Moreover, the (energy) transition to decarbonised economies (and e-mobility) and full circular economy implementation implies continuous innovation in materials and in low-carbon energy technologies.

The European Raw Materials Initiative was put forward in 2008 to tackle the challenges related to the access to raw materials. Given the continued strategic importance of raw materials for the EU manufacturing industry, antimony (Sb), amongst another 25 mineral raw materials, was added to the latest list of Critical Raw Materials (CRM) for Europe published in 2017 by the European Commission [(COM(2017) 490 final)].

LocalEnergy (<http://localenergy.ineg.pt/>) focuses on the valorisation of endogenous resources (solar and mineral) through the development of energy-harvesting applications based on the tetrahedrite mineral, which offers a high exploitation potential. Portugal has a high level of solar energy irradiation and has one of the most important volcanogenic massive sulphide districts in the world, the Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB), where tetrahedrite mineral series is locally one of the constituents. Moreover, tetrahedrites are the main source of copper and antimony (e.g. Blatz, 2008). Tetrahedrite is a class of copper antimony sulfosalt mineral (with general formula $Cu_{12-x}M_xSb_4S_{13}$, x is less or equal to 2), i.e., consisting of earth-abundant and relatively non-toxic elements, thus opening new opportunities for renewable energy applications. The substitution of antimony by arsenic gives rise to tetrahedrite ($Cu_{12}Sb_4S_{13}$) - tennantite ($Cu_{12}As_4S_{13}$) end-members of the solid solution. Metals (M) as Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Zn, Ag, Cd, In, Hg, Pb, Bi are structurally supported but natural tetrahedrites usually have the complex formula $(Cu,Ag)_{10}(Fe,Zn)_2(Sb,As)_4S_{13}$ (Wu and Peterson, 1977).

In this study, the Barrigão deposit is revisited in the light of tetrahedrite-tennantite importance for European CRM knowledge as well as material research for

development of thermoelectric (TE) and solar energy harvesting technologies.

1.1. Geological Setting of the Barrigão Mine

Barrigão, a copper-rich brecciated vein deposit (Fig. 1), is located in southern Portugal 10 km southeast of Neves Corvo, in the Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB). The deposit is structurally associated with a NE–SW striking fault zone inferred to have developed during late Variscan deformation. The ore is dominated by chalcopyrite + tennantite-tetrahedrite with minor arsenopyrite, pyrite, and löllingite. It is characterised by up to four ore-forming stages, with the late stages showing evidence of fluid-driven element re-mobilization (Reiser *et al.*, 2011). The supergene paragenesis is composed mainly of bornite, covellite, and digenite. The Barrigão deposit consists of two converging metric thick vein structures, extending approximately 1800 m along strike (Matos and Rosa, 2001; Matos *et al.*, 2003) and cross-cut Visean shales and greywackes of the Mértola Formation, a subunit of the Baixo Alentejo Flysch Group (Oliveira *et al.*, 2006). Several small secondary vein structures occur associated with the main structure.

Fig. 1 – Geological setting of the IPB and the location of the Barrigão deposit. A – Aljustrel; NC – Neves Corvo; B – Barrigão (adapted after Reiser *et al.*, 2011).

2. Materials and Methods

A 600 kg sample of ore was collected from the mine dump on site. Six hand selected composite samples were then crushed (1-2 mm and 2-4 mm) from where tetrahedrite-tennantite minerals were carefully selected and handpicked under

the binocular microscope (Fig. 2), for application in future tests to produce TE materials. All the selection process was accompanied by the control of the chemical analysis through a quick test (by direct irradiation of rock fragments and handpicked mineral grains concentrate) using a handheld portable X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (p-XRF, Genius 9000+7000 from Skyray Instrument Inc.) and by an X-ray diffraction (XRD) study to evaluate vestigial phases. It must be noted that with the p-XRF equipment used, the light elements (belowK) could not be measured. A Philips PW 1500 powder diffractometer with Bragg- Brentano geometry, equipped with a large- anode copper tube operating at 50 kV – 40 mA and a curved graphite crystal monochromator, was used for XRD.

To characterize the tetrahedrite-tennantite minerals, electron-probe microanalyses (EPMA) were carried out using a fully automated JEOL JXA-8500F microprobe, equipped with one energy dispersive (EDS) and five wavelength dispersive (WDS) spectrometers. A focused 20KV electron beam of 20 nA current was used to analyse the minerals in the samples.

Fig. 2 – Fragment dump rocks (above) and tetrahedrite-tennantite handpicked grains (below).

3. Results and Discussion

The quick chemical test performed from Barrigão mine dump rock fragments to almost pure mineral grains evidenced a gradual increment of Cu (from 3.1% to

26.7%), Fe (2.3 to 3.1%), Zn (0 to 0.3%), As (0.7 to 1.9%), Sb (0.4 to 1%) indicating an effective selection of tetrahedrite-tennantite minerals. The XRD pattern confirmed the presence of tetrahedrite-tennantite as the major phase, along with vestigial quartz, chalcopyrite as well as other undifferentiated mineral phases (Fig. 3). In spite of the inevitable presence of these minor phases, since some can be intergrown or hosted in tennantite (Reiser *et al.*, 2011), these results are good indicators of the adequate concentration of tetrahedrites for the application in TE tests. Preliminary microprobe data allowed calculating the approximate chemical formulas (normalized to 13S), considering the points with major contents of Sb and As respectively:

Fig. 3 – XRD pattern collected from powdered handpicked grains. Assigned phases: T- Tetrahedrite (JCPDF card nr. 24- 1318); CP- Chalcopyrite, CuFeS_2 (nr. 9-423); Q-Quartz, SiO_2 (nr. 5-0490).

The present data support the dominant occurrence of the tennantite end-member composition (as mentioned by Ferreira *et al.*, 1995; Reiser *et al.*, 2011), although tetrahedrite end-member composition occurs in hydrothermal overprint parageneses (Reiser *et al.*, 2011). The Ag, Zn, Hg, Fe and Sb content reaches 0.07 wt%, 2.27 wt%, 0.1 wt%, 8.04 wt% and 15.54 wt%, respectively. The results obtained by Levinsky *et al.* (2019) on tetrahedrite-tennantite solid solutions $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_{4-x}\text{As}_x\text{S}_{13}$ ($0 \leq x \leq 4$) synthesized by powder metallurgy show that As has neither a beneficial nor a detrimental influence on the thermoelectric properties of tetrahedrites. Consequently, the thermoelectric properties of TE materials

processed from mixtures of natural and synthetic tetrahedrites should also be insensitive to the Sb-to-As ratio present in the natural tetrahedrite - tennantite minerals.

4. Conclusions

The transition to a circular economy is essential to develop a sustainable, low C, resource efficient, and a competitive EU economy. In this context, CRM are of great importance to the EU economy. Improving the circular use of CRM is a key strategy for securing the security of supply and an objective of various EU policy documents, e.g. action #39 of the Circular Economy Action Plan: "Sharing of best practice for the recovery of critical raw materials from mining waste and landfills" [SWD(2019) 90 final]. The Barrigão mine dump contains appreciable quantities of CRM that fall within the scope of this action plan.

As ore treatment procedures become more efficient, Barrigão's potential for Ge and Ag may increase even though the mineralised vein is approx. 1800m long (Reiser *et al.*, 2011) and the tailings volume reduced given the small scale mining operation undertaken thus far.

The energy transition to a decarbonised energy system implies more progress in all aspects related with renewable technologies, including the research and innovation of new and improved materials, e.g., materials for harvesting energy from renewable sources or for converting wasted energy into electricity. Considering that the current TE materials and chalcogenide thin-film solar cells are based on rare and/or toxic elements, it is imperative to shift the focus to materials that are inexpensive, easy to synthesize, environmentally friendly and based on earth-abundant elements. The tetrahedrite-tennantite series are one of such class of materials and its presence in the Barrigão mine dump, and the possibility of its direct use in the TE materials processing, is viewed as relevant and strategic resource for the development of innovative energy-harvesting applications.

Aknowledgements

This work was funded by the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P., under the project

LocalEnergy "Local Resources for Multifunctional Tetrahedrite-based Energy-Harvesting Applications" (PTDC/EAM-PEC/29905/2017) and INCA "Characterization of Crucial Mineral Resources for the Development of Renewable Energy Technologies: The Iberian Pyrite Belt Ores as a Source of Indium and Other High- Technology Elements" (PTDC/CTE-GIN/67027/2006). The authors are grateful to J. Marquilhas, M. Silva, J. Fernandes, and to an anonymous reviewer and F. Noronha.

References

- Blatz, P., 2008. Mechanochemistry in Nanoscience and Minerals Engineering. Publisher Springer Science & Business Media, 413 p. ISBN 3540748555, 9783540748557.
- COM (2017) 490 final, 2017. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the council, the european economic and social committee and the committee of the regions on the 2017 list of Critical Raw Materials for the EU. SWD(2019) 90 final, 2019. Commission Staff Working Document.
- Ferreira, J.A., Figueiredo, M.O., Gaspar, O.C. 1995. Estudo cristalquímico preliminar das tetraedrites do jazigo de cobre filoniano do Barrigão (Faixa Piritosa Portuguesa). Memória nº4, Museu Lab. Miner. Geol. Univ. Porto, 625- 627.
- Levinsky, P., Candolfi, C., Dauscher, A., Tobola, J. Hejtmanekb, J., Lenoir, B., 2019. Thermoelectric properties of the tetrahedrite-tennantite solid solutions $Cu_{12}Sb_4-yAs_yS_{13}$ and $Cu_{10}Co_2Sb_4-yAs_yS_{13}$ ($0 \leq x, y \leq 4$). Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys., 21, 4547-4555.
- Matos, J.X., Rosa, C. 2001. Diagnóstico Preliminar de Minas Abandonadas. In: Área Sul. Internal Report, IGM.
- Matos, J.X., Martins, L., Rosa, C. 2003. Parque Mineiro da Cova dos Mouros: IGM contribute for the sustainable development of the mining park. Instituto Geológico y Minero de España, Cuadernos del Museo Geominero, 2, 487-494.
- Oliveira, J.T., Relvas, J.M.R.S., Pereira, Z., Matos, J.X., Rosa, C.J., Rosa, D., Munhá, J., Jorge, R., Pinto, A. 2006. O Complexo vulcano-sedimentar da Faixa Piritosa: estratigrafia, vulcanismo, mineralizações associadas e evolução tectono-estratigráfica no contexto da zona Sul Portuguesa. In: Dias, R., Araújo, A., Terrinha, P. Kulberg, J.C. (Eds). Geologia de Portugal no contexto da Íberia, Univ. Évora, 207-244.
- Reiser, F.K.M., Rosa, D.R.N., Pinto, Á.M.M., Carvalho, J.R.S., Matos, J.X., Guimarães, F.M.G., Alves, L.C., de Oliveira, D.P.S. 2011. Mineralogy and geochemistry of tin- and germanium-bearing copper ore, Barrigão remobilized vein deposit, Iberian Pyrite Belt, Portugal. International Geology Review, 53, 1212-1238.
- Wu, I., Peterson, U., 1977. Geochemistry of Tetrahedrite and Mineral Zoning at Casapalca, Peru. Economic Geology, 72, 993-1016

Casos

Abrantes, F.	61
Abreu Marques, R.	161
Abreu, M.M.	427, 449, 453
<u>Adánez Sanjuán, P.</u>	27
Afonso, P.	79
Albardeiro, L.	87, 269
Albuquerque, T.	57, 375
Almeida, A.	515
Almeida, C.	319
Almeida, S.F.P.	419
Álvarez, R.	445
<u>Alves, A.R.A.</u>	431
<u>Andrade, C.</u>	307, 323
<u>Anes Garcia, N.</u>	345
Antelo, J.	449
António, A.	65
<u>Antunes, M.</u>	133, 333, 461
Arán, D.	449
Araújo, A.	35, 39, 57, 153, 505
Araújo, J.	35, 39, 57
Araújo, R.	203
Araújo, V.	269
Arévalo-Lomas, L.	445
Arranz-González, J.C.	383
Azevedo, M.R.	61, 99, 125, 129, 329
Bacedoni, M.	341
Baragaño, D.	355
Barbero, L.	415
Barrio-Parra, F.	445
Barrulas, P.	217, 259
<u>Batista, A.</u>	289
Batista, M.J.	79, 269
Bel-Lán, A.	265, 375
Benavente, D.	53
Benoit, M.	103
Bento dos Santos, T. ..	71, 83, 95, 103, 107, 149
Berrezueta, E.	217
Biosca, B.	445
Blanco-Quintero, I.F.	53
Blázquez, A.	31, 43
Bobos, I.	145, 277
<u>Boente, C.</u>	355, 375
Borrego, P.	341
Brás, A.	333
Bryka, K.	411
Cabral Pinto, M.	461, 515
Cachapuz, P.	71, 83
Callaba, A.	519
Campos, M.J.	465
Caperta, A.	453
Cardoso-Fernandes, J.	273
Carneiro, A.	505
Carneiro, J.	217
Carnero, F.	199
Carvalho, C.	161, 277
Carvalho, D.R.	71, 83, 149
Carvalho, M.R.	367
Carvalho, P.C.S.	65, 293
Casas, M.	437
Casas-Ruiz, M.	415
Cavalcanti, D.E.	169
Cave, M.	371
Cerqueira, Â.	23
Chacón-Baca, E.	399
Chichorro, M.	83, 149
Cienfuegos, P.	359
Coello, X.	395
Colina, A.	355
<u>Córdoba, F.</u>	341, 387, 399, 407, 411, 419, 469, 473, 477
Corfu, F.	129
<u>Cortinhas, A.</u>	453
<u>Costa e Silva, S.</u>	285
Costa, C.	23, 371
Costa, J.J.	461
<u>Costa, M.</u>	501
Costa, M.M.	129
<u>Cotrim, B.</u>	103
Coutinho, R.	307, 323
Covelli, S.	359
Cruz, J.V.	307, 323
Cunha, P.P.	191
<u>Curcio, A.C.</u>	415
Curiel, J.	403
Davila, J.M.	419, 473, 477
Dávila, J.M.	387, 399, 403, 407, 411, 469
De la Torre, M.J.	465
<u>De Miguel, E.</u>	445
<u>De Oliveira, D.</u>	255, 269
De Soto, I.S.	437
<u>Dias, M.</u>	231
Dias, M.I.	511
Dias, R.	75, 157, 505

Diáz-Curiel, J.	419, 445
Díaz-Somoano, M.	351
Díez-Montes, A.	87
Domingos, F.	489, 493
Duarte, B.	161
Duarte, L.V.	179, 183, 195, 489
Duarte, P.	319
Durães, N.	329, 419, 423
Eguilior, S.	213
Esperancinha, S.	141
Espinha Marques, J.	315, 457
Faria, T.G.	165
Fatela, F.	49
Fernandes, J.	319
Fernández-Gutierrez del Álamo, L.	445
Ferreira da Silva, E.A.	23, 367, 403, 419, 431, 441, 515
Ferreira Gomes, J.	1
Ferreira, J.A.	95, 107
Ferreira, L.	329
Ferreira, S.L.M.	161
Ferreira, T.C.	453
Figueira, E.	419
Figueiras, J.	235, 301
Filipe P.	239
Flor-Blanco, G.	359
Flores, D.	175, 187, 191, 203, 315, 391, 457
Fonseca, B.	423
Fonseca, C.	195
Fonseca, R.	35, 39, 57
Fontolan, G.	359
Forján, R.	355
Fortes, J.C.	387, 399, 403, 407, 411, 419, 469, 473, 477
Francisco, P.	223
Freitas, M.	61
Galacho, C.	217
Galán, L.A.	31, 43
García de Madinabeitia, S.	7
García- del-Cura, M.A.	53
García Martínez, M.J.	383, 395
García, N.	355
García-Giménez, R.	437
García-Ordiales, E.	359, 363
Gaspar, M.	223, 227, 281
Gil Iburguchi, J.I.	7
Giménez-Forcada, E.	311, 337
Gméling, K.	511
Gomes, A.S.	49
Gomes, E.	141, 293, 461
Gomes, M.E.	99
Gonçalves, A.	243
Gonçalves, M.A.	11, 259
Gonçalves, P. A.	175
Grácio, N.	281
Grande, J.A.	387, 399, 403, 407, 411, 419, 469, 473, 477
Grima, J.	337
Guedes, A.	145, 209, 285
Guerner Dias, A.	423
Guimarães, F.	255
Guise, L.	49
Guzmán, M.	199
Guzmán-Martínez, F.	383
Hidalgo, M.C.	465
Hurtado, A.	213
Inácio, M.	515
Izquierdo-Díaz, M.	445
Jesus, A.P.	103
Jiménez, J.	337
Jiménez, S.	395
Jordt-Evangelista, H.	165
Jorge, M.P.	497
Laranjeira, V.	187
Leal, S.	239, 247
Leiva, M.	403, 411
Lézin, C.	195
Lima, A.	247, 273, 289
Lima, J.	273
Lima, J.Z.	441
Lima, L.	111
Lima, M.N.	169
Llamas Borrajo, J.	27, 213, 519
Llamas, J.F.	379, 519
Lobarinhas, D.	227
Locutura, J.	265
Lopes, J.C.	493
Lopes, L.	493, 505
López, P.I.	199
López-Cilla, I.	31, 43
López-Ramírez, J.A.	415
Loredo, J.	359, 363
Luís, A.C.M.	65
Luís, A.T. ..	387, 399, 403, 407, 411, 419, 469, 473, 477
Luis, D.	351

Luque, J.A.	337
Luque-Espinar, A.	311
Ma, L.	213
Macías, F.	449
Madureira, P.	259
Magalhães, J.	91
Magalhães, V.	61
Maia, M.	79, 153, 251
Mansilha, C.	315
Manteca, I.	31, 43
Marcelo, J.	293
Marinho Reis, P.	371, 461
Marinho, M.	91
Marques de Sá, C.	277
Marqués Sierra, A.L.	345
Marques, A.C.P.	367
Marques, M.M.	191
Marques, R.	23, 511
Marques, R.A.	165
Márquez, G.	199
Martínez, J.	465
Martínez-Frías, J.	19, 487
Martín-Méndez, I.	265, 375
Martins, F.	99
Martins, H.C.B.	115
Martins, I.	227, 235
Martins, Z.	487
Massimo B.	217
Mata, J.	95, 103, 107, 119
Matanzas, N.	355
Mateus, A.	231, 235, 301
Matias Lopes, J.A.	487
Matos, J.X.	79, 87, 251, 269
Mazadiego, L.	445
Medeiros-Junior, E.B.	91, 161, 165
Medina, J.	125, 129
Medina, R.	445
Melo, V.M.M.	481
Mendes, P.	297
Mendonça Filho, J.G.	175, 183, 187, 195
Mendoza, R.	465
Midões, C.	319
Miguel, C.	217
Milisse, D.	203
Mirão, J.	217, 259, 269, 501
Moita, P.	217, 259
Monteiro, F.	427, 453
Morais, I.	87, 269
Moreira, K.	209
Moreira, N.	75, 149, 153, 157, 187, 505
Moreno, F.	49
Moreno, J.	49
Moreno-Ventas, I.B.	341
Moura, A.	293
Moura, H.	191
Mourinha, N.	505
Muñoz, P.	31, 43
Navarro, F.	31, 43
Neves, F.	255
Neves, O.	515
Nhamutole, N.	203
Noack, Y.	371, 461
Noqueira Neto, J.A.	99, 169
Nogueira, P.	35, 39, 57, 79, 153, 187, 251, 297
Nolan, J.	129
Noronha, F.	75, 111, 137, 145, 239, 243, 247, 285
Novo, L.A.B.	431
Oliveira, A.	115
Oliveira, O.M.C.	481
Oliveira, P.T.M.	481
Oliveira, R.	461
Ordoñez, A.	445
Ordóñez, S.	53
Ortega, M.	395
Ortiz, J.E.	31, 43, 379, 519
Pacheco, N.	269
Pardo, E.	337
Patinha, C.	423, 441
Paula, D.	91, 161, 165
Pedro, J.	75, 153, 157, 217, 297, 505
Pereira, A.J.S.C.	141, 179, 493, 497
Pereira, A.R.	259
Pereira, I.	95, 107
Pereira, V.	515
Pinheiro, L.	61
Pinho, C.	35, 39, 57
Pinto Ribeiro, L.	119
Pinto, E.	515
Pinto, F.	235
Portela, L.	125
Prudêncio, M.I.	23, 511
Queiroz, A.F.S.	481
Ramallo, S.	31, 43
Ramos, V.	137, 239

Rangel, M.J.....	461
Reiser, F.....	255
Rey, J.....	465
Ribeiro da Costa, I.....	301
Ribeiro, A.....	75, 157
Ribeiro, J.....	187, 191, 315, 351, 391, 457
Ribeiro, S.....	125, 329
Rocha, F.....	23, 371, 461
<u>Rocha, J.</u>	315, 457
Roda-Robles, E.....	273
Rodrigues, A.L.....	511
<u>Rodrigues, B.</u>	183
Rodrigues, M.....	49, 145
Rodrigues, P.....	235, 301
Rodrigues, V.G.S.....	441
Rodríguez Estrella, T.....	31, 43
Rodríguez Gallego, J.L.....	355, 375
Rodríguez-Valdés, E.....	355
Romão, J.....	71, 75, 149, 157
Romero, P.....	395
Romero, S.....	411
Roqueñí, N.....	359, 363
Ros, M.....	31, 43
<u>Rosa, A.R.</u>	71, 119
Rosado, L.....	269
<u>Roseiro, J.</u>	79, 153, 251, 301
Russo, D.....	23
Salgado, L.....	355
Salgueiro, E.....	61
Salgueiro, R.....	87, 255, 281
Sánchez, I.....	437
<u>Sánchez-Palencia, Y.</u>	31, 43, 379, 519
Sant'Ovaia, H.....	115, 243, 289
Santiago, C.S.....	169
<u>Santillana, E.</u>	3
Santisteban, M.....	387, 399, 403, 407, 411, 419, 469, 473, 477
<u>Santos, A.</u>	399
<u>Santos, A.C.</u>	209
Santos, E.S.....	449
Santos, J.F.....	461, 505
<u>Santos, M.V.S.</u>	481
Santos, P.....	223, 231, 315, 457
Sanz-Prada, L.....	363
São Pedro, D.....	79, 297
Sarmiento, A.M.....	387, 399, 403, 407, 411, 419, 469, 473, 477
<u>Sêco, S.L.R.</u>	179, 489
Sequeira Braga, A.....	371
Silva Júnior, J.B.....	481
<u>Silva, M.M.V.G.</u>	65
Silva, R.L.....	179, 183
Silva, T.P.....	255
Simões, N.....	497
Solá, A.R.....	71, 83, 87, 149
Sousa, M.....	75
Souza, B.C.C.....	165
Souza, K.H.S.....	481
Suárez-Ruiz, I.....	191, 203, 351
Tassinari, C.....	99
Teixeira, M.....	419
Teixeira, T.....	125
Teodoro, A.C.....	273
Tomillo, P.....	351
Torres, T.....	31, 43, 379, 519
Valbuena, C.....	477
<u>Valente, T.</u>	15, 49, 371
Valentim, B.....	209
Valera, A.C.....	511
Valladares, C.....	161
Valle Aguado, B.....	99, 129
Valverde Vaquero, P.....	71
Vandenabeele, P.....	501
Velasco, T.C.....	165
Vicente, S.....	251
<u>Vidigal, P.</u>	427
Vieira, C.....	49
Vigil de la Villa, R.....	437
Viveiros, F.....	307, 323
Wach, G.....	179
Watson, N.....	179
Wragg, J.....	371
Zhang, R.....	239

ORGANIZAÇÃO | ORGANIZACIÓN

UNIVERSIDADE
DE ÉVORA

ICT

Instituto de Ciências da Terra

Consejo Superior de Colegios
de Ingenieros de Minas

Colegio Oficial
Químicos
de Madrid

ILUSTRE COLEGIO OFICIAL
DE GEÓLOG@S

1978-2018
40 AÑOS DEFENDIENDO LA PROFESIÓN

Asociación de
Químicos e
Ingenieros Químicos
de Madrid

ZM-3D

Modelos Metalogénicos 3D da Zona de Ossa-Morena
Valorização dos Recursos Minerais do Alentejo